

The Roman courtesan Julia da Gallese (1529–1565); her life and fortune

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This is the story of Julia, born in 1529 in the village of Gallese, and brought to Rome by her mother when she was small. At the age of 14 years Julia was engaged to marry Orazio Alidosi, but if she actually married, her husband almost immediately disappeared. The year after, now aged 15 years, Julia became a courtesan. Fortuitously, some of her account books have survived. They include material sufficient to reconstruct the vivid outlines of her life, including her close relationships with her mother, Francesca, and with the nobleman Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino. Julia's papers are now in the archive of the Biblioteca Corsiniana in Rome, in the collection entitled *Pia Casa degli orfani di Santa Maria in Aquiro*, with the press-mark SMA.¹ Thus, references in the following essay such as SMA 152.20 should be read as tome 152, folio 20. Some tomes lack folio numbers.

1. Kolega 2015

The village where Julia was born, Gallese, is about 50 km north of Rome, and a few kilometres from the River Tiber. With its maze of narrow alleys the village remains little altered from Julia's day, mainly due to its peculiar isolation. The only changes that a visitor from the past might note are that the houses have been modernized, and their inhabitants are in peculiar, modern dress. The village population is now about 2000, probably much the same as in the sixteenth century.

Although Rome was then a forge of European culture Julia, on arrival, would have probably have seen only a city dissolute, violent and rich, with the riches almost entirely in the hands of the cardinals and nobles. It would have seemed huge, even if it had but 50 000 inhabitants. In common with Gallese were the filthy, muddy, unpaved streets. As for her prospects, there were few. The majority of girls like her were destined to be wives, or servants. It was decided that it would be the former. Julia's father, Roberto Tagliacozzo, is not mentioned at this point and was presumably already dead.

Julia was to marry Orazio de Alidosi, a widower with two small sons.² The Alidosi were a noble family from Imola, but Orazio Alidosi despite his nobility, was evidently far from rich. Another member of the family, Ottavio Alidosi (†1546), was the trusted domestic servant (*cubicularius*) of pope Paolo III (i.e. Alessandro Farnese the elder), and a member of the household (*famigliare*) of Cardinal Alessandro Farnese the younger.³

2. SMA 26.1r

3. Forcella 1869,
vol. 1, n° 1308

The dowry that Orazio was evidently content with was a modest 150 scudi. Of this, Julia's mother had already paid 25 scudi, but needed six months to pay the rest. To appreciate the size of the dowry it may be recalled that in 1564 poor girls from deprived backgrounds, daughters of *Cortegiane, ò Donne di mala vita, e persone d'estrema povertà* who were educated in the newly completed convent of Santa Caterina de' Funari, in Rome, were provided with dowries of about 60 scudi.¹ In 1580, Montaigne recorded the annual ceremony at which poor girls were given dowries of 35 scudi by the pope in S. Maria sopra Minerva, intended to save them from prostitution.² These data make Julia's dowry of 150 scudi seem quite respectable. However, noblewomen at this time would have had dowries of at least 1000 scudi.³ The scudo, it should be said, was a tiny gold coin weighing slightly over 3 g, divided into 10 juli and 100 baiocchi, with a present-day bullion value of about 150 euro.

1. Piazza 1698, p. 182

2. Montaigne 1889, pp. 317-318

3. Calcaterra 2004, pp. 142-146

The date of the marriage with Orazio Alidosi is uncertain, for only an undated extract from the marriage contract survives. It was probably in 1543, when Julia reached the age of 14 years and would be generally regarded as marriageable. The marriage, however, must have come to a swift end, for Orazio Alidosi never appears subsequently in Julia's life.

On reaching 15 years in 1544 Julia changed her plans, perhaps having discovered that for her, marriage was equivalent to being an unpaid domestic servant and concubine. Furthermore, if her husband had died Julia would have found that she would get her dowry back, but no more; her husband's wealth, such as it was, would have been inherited by his sons. So Julia decided, perhaps persuaded by her mother, to become a courtesan, i.e. a superior kind of prostitute. It is to be hoped that Julia's mother explained to her the reality of prostitution. Veronica Franco (1546-1591), a Venetian courtesan celebrated for her poetry, and with long experience of the profession, wrote a letter to the mother of a girl contemplating the career with a series of questions to point out its horrors – though failing to mention the rosy prospect of financial independence;

darsi in preda di tanti, con rischio d'esser dispogliata, d'esser rubbata, d'esser uccisa; ch'un solo un dì ti toglia quanto con molti in molto tempo hai acquistato con tant'altri pericoli d'ingiurie, & d'infermità contagiose, & spaventose? mangiar con l'altrui bocca, dormir con gli occhi altrui, muoversi secondo l'altrui desiderio, correndo in manifesto naufragio sempre della facoltà, & della vita, qual maggior miseria? quai ricchezze, quai commodità, quai delitie posson acquistar un tanto peso? Credete a me, tra tutte le sciagure mondane questa è l'estrema; ma poi se s'aggiungeranno à i rispetti del mondo quei dell'anima, che perdizione, & che certezza di dannatione è questa?⁴

4. Franco 1580, pp. 44-45; cf. Masson 1975, p. 165

to make yourself the prey of many, with risk of being stripped of everything, robbed, murdered; in a day, to lose everything gained over many years through such risky labours, not to mention catching contagious and horrible illnesses? Eat with the mouth of someone else, sleep with the eyes of someone else, move at the whim of someone else, racing towards the obvious destruction of your mind, and life, what greater misery could there be? What wealth, what convenience, what delight can be had at such a price? Believe me, beside all the misfortunes of the world this is the worst; but adding to that the perdition of your soul, what result can one expect but eternal damnation?

If Julia was thus warned it had not the desired effect; she went ahead anyway. She rented a house in an area which, in 1549, was described as *Da Francia*. This was near the then French embassy, close to the present Piazza di Spagna.¹ It was a financially attractive location for courtesans, for sixteen others lived close by. In consequence of having a house at her disposal Julia attracted the attention of the Bargello di Corte Savella (the criminal court dealing with papal dependants), and found herself listed as a courtesan (*curialis* in official latin documents) – something she would have doubtless preferred to have avoided, since it rendered her liable to non-recurrent (i.e. one-off) taxation.

1. Mendoza 2016, pp. 141 & 241

Julia's mother, Francesca, who had probably once been a courtesan, stayed with her in her new home until she died some ten years later. The suggestion that Julia's mother was a courtesan is not at all unlikely for there are numerous instances of mothers and daughters succeeding each other in this field, both in the 1549 tax roll and in the literature of the period – one could cite, for example, the much celebrated Veronica Franco and Tullia d'Aragona, both introduced to the profession by their mothers. Francesca could well be the *Francisca cortesana* in Campo Marzio in 1527.² The 1527 census of Rome was prepared on the eve of the sack of Rome, after which most of the surviving inhabitants of the city deserted it. Francesca probably went back to Gallese and may have married there, returning to Rome later.

2. Lee 1985, p. 55, n° 2160

The prostitutes of Rome in 1549

The material wealth of Rome started rising noticeably at the start of the sixteenth century, together with prostitution. In 1520 pope Leo X complained of 'licentious women who lead an ignoble and sordid life in the city we love, whose number (alas!) is increasing day by day due to the depravity of the times we live in...'.³ The Church, however, could not overlook the fact that some of these licentious women made money, and were consequently subjected to occasional taxation. The 1549 tax roll entitled 'Tassa fatta alle cortigiane per la riparazione del ponte [di Santa Maria]' gives their location, the assessed rents for their premises, and the tax due.⁴ This tax was not annual; it was quite exceptional, in this case intended for the repair of the bridge over the Tiber called the *Ponte Santa Maria*, the remains of which are now known as the *Ponte Rotto*. The assessed rents that the 'courtesans' paid are summarized in Fig. 1, from which it appears that Julia's, at 40 scudi, was significantly higher than that paid by most of her colleagues. The tax she had to pay was 10% of the rental, i.e. 4 scudi. The total tax paid by the 437 women listed in the tax roll was 979 scudi.⁵ In addition Julia would have had to pay an annual tax of 1 scudo due from all prostitutes.⁶

3. Mendoza 2016, p. 280

4. Mendoza 2016

5. Mendoza 2016, p. 81

6. Mendoza 2016, pp. 185 et seq.

A distribution map shows the 'courtesans' to be highly concentrated in a small part of the city, near but not adjacent to the Vatican (Fig. 2). A cluster in the south-east part of the map area marks a group of 13 'courtesans' round the Palazzo Colonna, close to Piazza Venezia. Those near the Ponte Sisto were also close to the Palazzo Farnese. The location of the 'courtesans' evidently reflects the wealth and availability of clients. It must be emphasized, however, the list is far from complete. Most of the women come from the

Fig. 1. Histogram showing the distribution of rentals paid by 386 Roman courtesans in 1549, based on the tax roll of that year (Mendoza 2016, pp. 229–261). The histogram shows that the class interval between 10 and 20 scudi contained more courtesans than any other. The total number of courtesans in the tax roll is 433, but for many of them no rent is specified.

Fig. 2. Map showing the distribution of Roman courtesans in 1549, based on the tax list of that year. Each black symbol represents ten individuals. The river Tiber is tinted grey. Two localities where Julia da Gallese is known to have lived are shown, namely near Piazza di Spagna (PS) and l'Ortaccio (OR). The greatest concentration of courtesans is in *rione* Campo Marzio, centred on Sant' Agostino. The outlier in the south-east part of the map indicates courtesans around Palazzo Colonna, in *rione* Trevi. The only two bridges across the Tiber in the map area at that time were the Ponte Sisto and the Ponte Sant' Angelo.

districts of Campo Marzio and Regola. There were few from Colonna, Parione, Pigna and Sant'Eustachio, and none at all from Borgo, Trevi, Ripa, Campitelli, Monti, Sant'Angelo, and Trastevere. It seems as if the list was compiled by enumerators from the Corte Savella in Regola who already knew where to find the majority of prostitutes, and aimed to get the maximum revenue with the least effort.

The term 'courtesan' requires comment, for the women listed were paying annual rentals ranging from 3 scudi to 150 scudi. It is clear from the original list that those paying less than 20 scudi had only a single room and could hardly be described as anything but common prostitutes (*meretrici*). They account for 45% of the total. Consequently, only about a half of the 437 women in the tax roll were occupying entire houses, and could thus be regarded as real courtesans. They number about 200. The number in all Rome would be somewhat greater, perhaps 250.

Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino de Vinaya

The earliest documents regarding Julia and her mother, Francesca, also mention a man, whose relationship to the two women is enigmatic. He described himself in his testament of 1566 as 'Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino de Vinaya, Pisano'. Giovanni Francesco was born about 1505 in Pisa, and died in 1574 in Rome.¹ He was, therefore about 20 years older than Julia, and roughly the same age as her mother.

1. SMA tomo 14.

As a member of a noble Genoese family Giovanni Francesco represented their economic interests in Rome, including supervising construction of the Palazzo Pallavicino in Campo Marzio. His principal occupation, however, was as legal representative (*procuratore*) for the immensely rich Cardinal Alessandro Farnese (1520-1589). About 1569 he was nominated a canon of the basilica of Santa Maria Maggiore, in Rome, and presented the church with a nativity scene, designed by Tommaso dei Cavalieri and executed in marble by the sculptor Francesco Pietrasanta.² It was completed in 1570 and placed in the Cappella del Presepe, where it has remained. Giovanni Francesco was also *Elemosiniere del Papa*, meaning that he was responsible for all the charitable activities of the Roman Church.

2. SMA tomo 14

Giovanni Francesco patiently watched over Julia's economic interests until she died. From Julia's point of view this was fortunate, for otherwise she might have frittered away her very substantial earnings. Near the end of her life she nominated him executor of her testament.³ Julia's papers have survived only because they bundled up with those of Giovanni Francesco's, which ultimately found their way into the archive of the *Pia casa degli orfani di Santa Maria in Aquiro*.⁴

3. BARGINUS 1563

4. Kolega 2015

A courtesan

Julia's foray into prostitution was in September 1544 when she was about 15 years old. Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino's presence is immediately manifest in a contract for a loan of 50 scudi to Julia, intended to finance the cost of her new life.⁵ It gives the impression that the project had been forged beforehand in conjunction with Julia and her mother:

5. SMA 26.129r

Sia noto a chi legera la presente come Ma Julia de galese figlia di Ma franc^a si chiama debitrice di Ms franc^o Pallavicino di scudi cinquanta di Julii x per scudo quali li ha prestatato per il passato in piu volte amichevolmente li quale rinuntiando ad ogni expectione 13 di numero haverli havuti con la speranza di haverli [Julia] promette per pagarli in questo modo cioe dieci scudi il mese cominzando dal presente mese di octobre prossimo a verun insino ala finale satisfatione. Et a fede del vero m' ha fatto fare detta Ma Julia et Ms franc^o questa poliza a me Gonz^e albero questo di 18 di 7bre 1544.

The reader should note that Madama Julia de Galese, daughter of Madama Francesca, declares herself to be in debt to Messer Francesco Pallavicino to the extent of fifty scudi of 10 juli each, which he willingly lent her in 13 instalments, hoping to have them back. [Julia] promises to repay the money at the rate of 10 scudi per month, starting from next October. In truth, the above text was dictated to me, Gonzales Albero, by Madama Julia and Messer Francesco today, 18th of September 1544.

The 50 scudi had been advanced in instalments, doubtless to cover the cost of renting a house or apartment, and purchasing its furnishings. The first instalment of the scheduled repayments was made only a few days after the contract was signed, and the last instalment in April the following year. Julia was earning money, lots of it. The same year, she started keeping accounts of money spent and received, some of which have survived. The observation that Julia was keeping accounts has to be qualified, in that entries in her account books were actually written by men, who in the case of contracts like the one above were commissioned to do it, and named. The only certain example of Julia's handwriting is shown in Fig. 3. It should be said that the mere fact that she could write at all is remarkable, for most of Rome's inhabitants at this time were illiterate.

Julia's account book shows that between September 1545 and September 1546 she had an income of 130 scudi from clients, perhaps attracted by her youth.¹ Her income subsequently fell. In 1549 it was only 80 scudi,² and in 1551, 85 scudi.³ The money was always delivered by the client who would write in the account book that the money had been paid, and sign it. Occasionally the money was delivered by an intermediary.

Clients were charged either 10 scudi or 11 scudi for a visit – the standard rate for courtesans in Rome at this time.⁴ It may be presumed that a payment of 11 scudi indicates that clients stayed to dinner. It must be said that the motive of these very expensive visits was not only sexual. The clients found not only a luxurious environment, but a woman always sympathetic to their problems, fantasies, hopes and despairs, the object being to induce their return. Julia succeeded. A certain Giovanni Francesco Migliorelli returned to her five times in the year 1549 alone.

There is no evidence in Julia's cash accounts indicating that she had more than one client at a time, except, perhaps, in the inventory of the dining-room furniture of the house in which she died. Among other items this records three chairs upholstered with gilded leather (*sedie di corame vecchie*), one of which was 'for a woman' (Appendix 1, *f.* 180r).

It can be seen from the personal papers of the celebrated courtesan Isabella de Luna, which are also in the archive of the *Pia Casa*, that she charged her clients the same as Julia

1. SMA 152.54r

2. SMA 26.136v

3. SMA 26.141r

4. Brantôme 1876, p. 146

even though she was much better known. But there are two notable differences. Firstly, Isabella's income was much greater. In 1547 she earned 300 scudi. Secondly, her income came mainly in multiples of 11, showing that she entertained groups of men (and perhaps women) to dinner. For example, in the year 1547 nine clients paid 11 scudi, but another seven came in groups of two, three, or on one occasion, five.¹

1. SMA 26.132r

In September 1554, Julia appeared in an official document as a *curialis* for the last time.² She had sufficient rents deriving from her houses, roughly 100 scudi per year, to live in comfort in her own house and devote herself to Marzio, her newly born son.

2. VALERIUS 1554

The life of a courtesan

The financial details presented in the previous section give little idea of the reality of a courtesan's life. Courtesans were entertainers quite as much as anything else. Bandello's description of an evening with the courtesan Isabella de Luna, Lelio Capilupi, and others, comes to mind.³ Though such literature, written for entertainment, might be regarded as an unreliable source, the same picture comes from private letters. Such letters are less likely to embroider the facts, so part of one is reproduced below.⁴ It was written from Rome on 5 November 1546 by the erudite Lelio Capilupi,⁵ to his friend Pietro Pamfili, major domo for the duchess of Urbino. It describes events in Lelio's house in Rome:

3. Bandello 1554, novella 51.

4. Berra 1932, pp. 366-368
5. Mutini 1975

Quella napolitana mi è reuscita 'visu et opera' perchè a dirvi il vero in secreto, et non lo direte poi alla signora duchessa di Camerino che non si dia disciplina per gli peccati miei. Io ne ho voluto pigliar un buon pasto, ho dormito con lei, anzi vegliato, il che non ho fatto con altra cortigiana poichè venni a Roma. Oltre il piacer del letto hebbi grandissimo passatempo a cena et dapoi, perchè invitai molti gentiluomi et feci nozze solenni. Erarvi de signalati il signor Lorenzo Strozza et tre genovesi ricchissimi, de quali eravi messer Tobia Pallavicino, il quale prima che questa signora venisse a Roma si intertenne con un'altra giovane, alla quale havea offerto di far le spese di pan et di vino et dargli il mese xv ducati, con patto che qualche fiata se la potessi menar in casa, a che la madre, roffiana vecchia, non havea voluto consentire si per tenerla più in reputation, non la lasciando uscir di casa per Roma che non le fosse levata di casa.

Hor la vecchia havendo inteso che messer Tobia havea dormito con la napolitana lo mandò a chiamar et a dirgli che voleva far quel che gli piacesse; egli non vi andò mai et quel dì che venne la signora qui a cena che fu mercordi passato lo mandò a richiamar di novo, et esso le mandò a dire che venisse qui in casa alla sera se gli voleva parlare et che si vederebbe se havea fatto buon cambio.

Nel punto proprio che volevamo andar a tavola, ecco che la vecchia con la figlia comparve condotta da un gentiluomo spagnolo detto il Baron, ricco di cinquemila ducati d'entrata, et fu quello che donò la cathena alla napolitana et venne con questa altra signora per vedere. La napolitana intendendo la venuta di questa altra signora, se ne fuggì in una camera et molto dolendosi di me innocente, dicendo che l'haveva tradito, nè mai si risolse di venir fuori in fin che tutti non li giurassimo ch'essa era più bella assai, come è ancho in effetto. Con questa fiducia uscì et raccolse l'altra signora et sederon a preso a tavola, stando però la napoletana come patrona et più bella in capo di tavola, niuna di loro mangiava, ma si guardavano come due combattenti et l'una l'altra pungendo messer Tobia. Sopra che si disse di molte cose et ciò che si diceva era preso in male parte dalla signora forestiera, a cui venner le lacrime agli occhi; et se sua madre non si levava a condurla via credo che ambe due s'haverian dato de' pugni. Ma si partì a mezza cena salutando tutti salvo che la napoletana. Il Baron andò a compagnarla.

Partita che fu, la napolitana disse de brave parole a messer Tobia, il quale si scusava il meglio che sapeva dicendo che non credeva che mai fosse stata sì pazza che havebbe voluto venir ad un tanto paragon; perchè tutti pregavano per lui. Ma si, ella per dargli martello si levò da tavola et ne venne a basciar tutti ch'eravamo dieci, pregandoci per quel bascio che non volessimo mai più pregar per lui. Di che assai si rise.

Finita questa osculatione, ecco il Baron arrivò che volse finir di cena et disse, ch'è persona molto arguta, tanta robba che ne fece morir di ridere, dolendosi che la signora havebbe mostrato sol gelosia di messer Tobia et non di lui che haveva menato quella signora, onde mostrava di prezzarlo molto poco essendo stato il primo che in Roma l'havebbe honorata.

Finita la comedia gli sposi andarono a letto, et la trovai una robba divina, et le usai cortesia la mattina di due belle camiscie lavorate di bianco et de due para di calze di seta, che m'havea portato messer Uberto da Mantova, et ambe due rimasino contenti et pranzò meco stando quasi tutto il dì in consolation tra noi di casa et cantò molte canzonette napoletane.

I have found out at first hand what the Napolitan woman is like, but you must keep it a secret and not say anything to the Duchess of Camerino else she find some way to punish me for my sins. I had a good dinner and then slept with her; or, I should say didn't sleep, which is something that hasn't happened with any other courtesan since I arrived in Rome. Quite apart from the pleasure of the bed I had a marvellous time at dinner; and after, because I had invited lots of friends and we solemnly celebrated the 'wedding'. I should mention Lorenzo Strozza and three very rich Genoese, including Tobia Pallavicino, who, before the Napolitan came to Rome, had amused himself with another young woman, to whom he had offered the cost of food and wine and 15 ducats a month if she would come to his house occasionally. But that bawd, her old mother, would not consent to such a thing, and for the sake of the girl's reputation would not let her leave home in Rome unless she was collected.

The old woman having heard that *messer* Tobia had slept with the Napolitan sent him a message saying that he could do as he wished [with her daughter], but he never went. And the day when the Napolitan came here to dinner; which was last Wednesday, the old woman called *messer* Tobia again, but he replied that she and her daughter should come to my house that evening if they wanted to talk to him, and would be able see if he had been justified in his choice.

At the moment when everyone was about to sit down to dinner; the old woman and her daughter arrived in company of a Spanish gentleman called the Baron, who had an income of 5000 ducats. It was he who had given a necklace to the Napolitan woman, and now had come with the other girl to visit. The Napolitan fled into another room, complaining, despite my innocence, that I had betrayed her; and would not come out until everyone had sworn that she was much more beautiful than her rival, which was true. Thus reassured she emerged and greeting the other *signora* they sat down next to each other at table, with the Neapolitan at the head as if she were not only the mistress of the house but also the more beautiful. Neither of them eat a morsel, but kept looking daggers at each other; while both of them needled *messer* Tobia. Much was said about him, but whatever it was the Napolitan took it badly. Tears came to the visiting *signora*, and if her mother had not led her away I believe that the two women would have come to blows. Halfway through dinner she left, greeting everyone but the Napolitan. The Baron accompanied her.

Now that she had left, the Napolitan expressed her feelings in no uncertain manner to *messer* Tobia, who did his best to excuse himself by saying that he never could have imagined that she [the visitor] would have been so mad as to come and allow herself to suffer such a comparison; so we all tried to justify him. But to add insult to injury the Napolitan got up from the table and kissed all ten of us, demanding in return that we abandoned our attempts to justify Tobia. We all laughed.

The kissing done, the Baron returned to finish his dinner, and, being very witty, related so many amusing anecdotes that we almost died of laughing. He much lamented that the girl he had brought with him should have been so jealous of *messer* Tobia rather than himself, showing how little regard she had for him despite her being his first conquest in Rome.

The comedy now over, we ‘newlyweds’ [Lelio & the Napolitan] went to bed. She was simply divine and in the morning I presented her with two beautiful embroidered shirts and two pairs of silk stockings which had been brought from Mantua for me by *messer* Uberto. Both of us were content. She lunched with me at home and remained with us all day, and sung many Napolitan songs.

The men who shared this evening’s entertainment would have found the courtesan of their choice while riding on horse-back through some of the more promising parts of the city, like Campo Marzio, glancing into the trellised windows of ground-floor rooms. From a distance of over a metre, the rider could only have had a fleeting glimpse of the woman, but the courtesan inside, with an eye close to the trellis, could clearly observe the man to judge his social position and wealth, and decide if to let him into her house. Montaigne comments on the extraordinary ability of Roman courtesans to allow men to see just enough to excite their imaginations, but no more.¹ The men mentioned in the letter above were, of course, wealthy. The Baron’s annual income compares with that of a Roman nobleman (1000–10000 scudi, or ducats), though no real nobleman would have felt obliged to boast about it. It should also be noted that the gifts given to the courtesans were in addition to the fees mentioned in the previous section.

1. Montaigne 1889, p. 301

The houses in Piazza di Monte d’Oro

By 1551 Julia had enough money to buy her first house, next to the Piazza di Monte d’Oro.² Prior to 1494 this area of Rome had been a vegetable garden (*orto*), hence its name l’Ortaccio.³ From Falda’s perspective view of Rome published in 1676 we see that the houses in the Piazza di Monte d’Oro were terraced, two or three stories high, with chimneys, and had back gardens. An estimate Julia requested for renovations to the house, dated 2 July 1551, is entitled ‘Misura et estima de lavori de muro de manufatura quali a fatti fare madonna julia da Galesio in una sua casa posta in Campo martio...’⁴ This estimate, on 25 closely written pages, reveals that the house, though only 50 years old, was practically a ruin. The total cost of the repairs was estimated at 307 scudi. Further repairs over the years 1555 to 1563 totalled another 726 scudi, though some of this may have been for other houses Julia had bought, mentioned in the inventory of her possessions (Appendix 1, f. 179r).

2. SMA 152.112r

3. Gnoli 1939, pp. 194–195

4. SMA 152.1r–7r

The restoration of the house was not just a whim, but a necessity for her profession. The eyes of a potential client would be drawn to a smartly presented house but repelled by a dingy one, whatever the qualities of the courtesan inside it.

The estimate for repairs reveals a typical townhouse of the period, on three floors, together with two cellars. There were ten rooms and a kitchen. Several rooms had fireplaces and above the roof towered seven chimney stacks, all of which had to be rebuilt. The floors of the house (excluding the cellars and kitchen), which were relaid with new terracotta tiles, covered 290 square metres.⁵ The new windows are not described as glazed,

5. SMA 152.2v: 6000 square palmi

so that probably had translucent waxed per panes guarded by wooden shutters. The frontage of the house onto the public road was 10 m, while at the back of the house there was a loggia facing onto a garden. The wooden stairs to the first and second floors were 1.3 m wide, giving ample room for two people, walking side by side. The rubble resulting from the work on the house was thrown into the muddy road outside.¹ Altogether the house appears to have been originally intended for a family of the merchant class, but evidently not big enough for Julia. In 1552 she commissioned an extension at the back, using part of the the garden.²

1. SMA 152.6v

2. SMA 152.117r

The reception room (*sala*) and one other room in the house had their newly plastered walls covered by panels of gilded leather (*corami*), a beautiful and very expensive material which in later centuries was substituted by wallpaper. Julia bought many. Panels costing 94 scudi were ordered from Giovanni Rusconi in July 1546,³ and still more in 1552 from the same craftsman costing 35 scudi.⁴ Giovanni Rusconi was a well-known Roman leather gilder (*auripellario*) who worked near Santa Lucia in Via dei Banchi Vecchi.⁵ Other wealthy courtesans doubtless had panels of gilded leather; Tullia d'Aragona had ten of them.⁶ They also adorned the rooms of noble houses, for example the Palazzo Chigi in Ariccia.⁷ Dutch paintings by Jan Vermeer and Pieter de Hooch show interiors with gilded leather panels completely covering the walls. In November 1550 Julia also bought 152 tapestry panels (*pani de ratza*) from Filippo Brando costing 103 scudi.⁸

3. SMA 152.57r

4. SMA 152.75r

5. Bertolotti 1884, pp. 66, 136, 138

6. ROMAULIS 1556b, f. 80v

7. Rodolfo & Volpi 2014

8. SMA 26.141r

The elaborate furnishings of Julia's house, intended to suit the tastes of her wealthy clientele, did not come close to those of the famous Roman courtesan Imperia Cognati (†1512), if we can believe the description given by the nobleman Angelo del Bufalo to Matteo Bandello, the novelist.⁹

9. Bandello 1554, novella XLII

It appears from the inventory of Julia's possessions compiled after her death in 1565 that she had left the house described above, probably in 1555, and died in a smaller house she owned next door.¹⁰ The inventory shows that it had six rooms on three floors, including a basement kitchen. It was one of the two houses Julia bequeathed to the Hospital of San Giacomo. When the Catasto Gregoriano was formed in 1824 the Hospital still owned one of these properties, at n° 89 and 90 Via dell'Arancio,¹¹ but Julia died next door, at n° 91, on the corner of Piazza di Monte d'Oro (*angulum versus plateam*).¹² All Julia's possessions were in this house, but any carpets, tapestries or gilded leather panels once present in the main house (*casa magna*) are missing, probably sold so that the house could be let unfurnished. One of her tenants in 1562 was the courtesan Armenia Mentebuona.¹³

10. BARGINUS 1565

11. Campomarzio Plate III, part. 382

12. BARGINUS 1565, f. 179r

13. SMA 152.44r

Julia's clients

The most striking thing about Julia's clients was their rarity. Her cash account books show that there was, on average, about one in six weeks, giving her ample time to display herself in public, and charm company in private. If the Giovanni Francesco Migliorelli mentioned earlier is indicative Julia would have only needed a clientele of two or three men to reach her income of about 100 scudi per year.

Julia wrote a volume of recollections entitled ‘Memorie diverse notate da Giulia (Tagliacozzi) da Gallese dell'anno 1555 al 1559’, which once formed tome 153 in the archive of the *Pia Casa*. The volume might have told us a great deal about Julia’s life and her clients, but a nineteenth century archivist discarded it, along with many others, as being of no material interest to the *Pia casa degli orfani*. Consequently, most of Julia’s clients are just names about whom little can be said. But a few were men who had not the ready cash to pay for their enchanting evenings with Julia and had to leave promissory notes. They were Pompeo Giustini, his brother Cosimo Giustini, and Tommaso Armentieri. Julia evidently decided to call in these debts when she retired, settling for interest-paying loans, or mortgages, instead of cash.

The nobleman Pompeo Giustini de Castello was the first to extinguish his debt by raising a mortgage (*censo*) over a property he owned in *rione* Parione in 1556. The mortgage was for 150 scudi at 10% interest¹ Julia was at home when she signed the contract, with Francesco Pallavicino beside her – which was just as well considering Pompeo’s character. The mortgage document is of particular interest for it describes Julia as the daughter of the ‘late Roberto Tagliacozzo of Gallese’. Julia also stated this in her testament. Tagliacozzo is a Jewish name, mainly found in Rome, which Julia never used except when notaries required it. She preferred to call herself Julia da Gallese.

1. ROMAULIS 1556a

Two years later, in January 1558, Julia granted an unsecured loan of 200 scudi at 12% interest to Cosimo Giustini de Castello, brother of the Pompeo just mentioned.² The contract contains a clause specifying Julia's son *Martii de Justinis* as her heir.

2. SMA 152.36r

In 1558 Cosimo was but a young man, not long graduated in law, but already a knight of the Order of San Pietro and subsequently a priest. In later life he commissioned the building of the Palazzo Giustini in Piazza Colonna, and accumulated an extensive collection of sculptures.³ He was murdered in 1603, at which time he was described as *referendario utriusque Signaturae*, i.e. a judge in the court of appeal of the Roman church.

3. Buccino 2011

The Giustini were a notable Roman family about which much has been written – see Thomas Cohen’s fascinating description of the trial of Pompeo Giustini in 1557, in which we discover that Pompeo was a brutal man who, when thwarted, was apt to use his hand to women and his sword to men⁴ He was brought to trial accused by his elder brother Ascanio of forcing their dying sister Vittoria, aged 15 years, to leave her dowry money to Pompeo and his brothers Pietro Paolo, Cosimo and Fabrizio, but not Ascanio and his sisters.

4. Cohen 2004, pp. 73–123

After the Giustini there followed a ‘loan’ by Julia to Tommaso Armentieri, in March 1559.⁵ Armentieri (†1565), was secretary and major-domo to Margherita d’Austria, daughter of the emperor Charles V and wife of Ottavio Farnese, Duca di Parma.⁶ Tommaso Armentieri was born in Salamanca and, to judge from the charitable bequests he made in his testament, very wealthy. The loan document, like that of Cosimo Giustini, was for 200 scudi at 12% interest, and nominates *Marti Justinis* (or Giustini) as Julia’s heir.

5. SMA 152.38r

6. Hunter 1996, p. 169

Despite their wealth these men were evidently living beyond their means. This is not surprising, for many of the richest men in sixteenth century Rome grossly overspent their

income on courtesans, gambling, and carriages, together with ostentatious projects like majestic buildings and art collections, making up the deficit by mortgaging their property.¹

1. Delumeau 1957,
vol. 1, p. 480

At almost the same time Julia was recouping unpaid credits, her rival, Isabella de Luna, was doing exactly the same. In 1559 Isabella had encountered the ingenuous young Neapolitan abbot Giovanni Domenico Surrentino and adroitly captured his affection.² In 1560 he practically lived with her, accumulating a debt of 2400 scudi for that year alone, far beyond his means to pay.³ To partially settle this debt he raised mortgages the same year totalling 1700 scudi, secured over property he owned near Naples.⁴

2. Lanciani 1903,
vol.2, p. 84

3. LOTTUS 1564
ff. 148r-149r

4. SMA 26.10r & 12r

5. SMA 152.40r-40v

Julia's last documented loan, of 100 scudi, was to Moses Rubini and his son in 1562.⁵ This was a profit sharing agreement concerned with the purchase and resale of textiles. It is not suggested here that Moses was a former client of Julia. A Jewish merchant would have had better things to do. Significantly, this loan was called in on 18 January 1565, probably to cover the cost of Julia's funeral a few weeks later.

Marzio

Julia's son Marzio is first mentioned in an instrument dated 11 September 1554.⁶ That same year the last page of one of Julia's account books is completely occupied by an elegantly written dedication to 'Signora Julia Gallese my dearest mistress'.⁷ It reads;

6. VALERIUS 1554

7. SMA 26.153r

Signora Julia gallese padrona mia carissima

*Dum Juga montis aper fluvios dum piscis amabit
Semper honos nomenque tuum laudesque manebunt*

The Latin verse is abbreviated from Virgil's fifth *Ecloga*, lines 76-78. It can be translated as 'while the boar loves the mountain top, and the fish the stream, your honour, name, and fame will forever endure'. It was clearly written by someone with a classical education, that could be almost any nobleman of the time.

Julia's mother Francesca remained with her daughter throughout her career but died in August 1553,⁸ leaving Julia to cope alone with her pregnancy. This seems to have been the point at which Julia decided to abandon her profession and start writing her memoirs. She engaged a wet-nurse for Marzio in January of the following year, 1555.⁹ This was a woman called Giovanna, the wife of Giovanni Bertero of Castel Novo in Piedmont, who had evidently lost her child and left her husband. The monthly wage she received was 10 *carlini* in cash, i.e. one *scudo*, in addition to which she would have had board and lodging. Giovanna remained with Julia for seven years, until May 1557;

8. SMA 152.76–
152.77

9. SMA 152.82r

Addi 10 de Maggio 1557

Per la presente si fa fede qualmente Giovanna piemontese serva della Ma Julia de gallese si chiama contenta et satisfatta dalla dicta ma Julia di tutto quello l'havesse servita tanto in dare latte al suo figliolo Martio quanto in servirla per serva per insino al dicto giorno 10 de Maggio 1557...¹⁰

10. SMA 26.156r

10th May 1557

The Piedmontese Giovanna, servant of Madama Julia de Gallesse here declares herself to be fully content and satisfied with the treatment she has had both as wet-nurse for Madama Julia's son Marzio and as her servant, up to the present day 10 May 1557.

After only a few weeks Giovanna returned, as recorded by Julia (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. The hand-writing of Julia da Gallesse, recording the return of her Piedmontese servant Giovanna on the first of June 1557; 'Memoria come giovanna piemontese torno a stare con me a di primo de giugno 1557'.¹

1. SMA 26.157v

Giovanna left Julia's service definitively in February 1562,² and was immediately followed by Antonina, who remained with Julia till she died. Julia seems to have been well pleased by Antonina, and in her testament left her 50 scudi together with her bed, a straw mattress, bed linen, her clothes and trinkets.³ The 50 scudi would have been roughly four times Antonina's annual salary.

2. SMA 26.207r

3. BARGINUS 1563, f. 176r

Julia's servants must have earned about 20 scudi, a year i.e. 12 scudi in cash and 8 scudi for their lodging. At this time the average salary of university teachers in Rome was about 300 scudi per year.⁴ This is 17 times greater than the wage of Julia's servants. Today this ratio would be about 4, illustrating the way that wealth in Renaissance Rome was concentrated in a tiny proportion of the population. The income of a noble Roman family at that time would have been at the very least 1000 scudi per year.

4. Renazzi 1803, vols. 2 & 3

Marzio's father

Marzio's surname was first mentioned four years after he was born, in January 1558, in the loan document for Cosimo Giustini, discussed earlier. Here he is referred to as *Martij de justinis*.⁵ One might suppose from this that Marzio was thought by Cosimo to be his son. But Julia also had had dealings with Cosimo's brother Pompeo Giustini, as described above, so doubt remains. The baptismal registers for the relevant parish, San Lorenzo in Lucina, offer no help, for the earliest dates from 1558 – too late to be useful.

5. SMA 152.36r

In any case, Julia was evidently content to accept that Marzio was the son of a Giustini, but four years later changed her mind. The trial of Pompeo Giustini in 1558–1559 may have been the cause, for all the men of that family, particularly Pompeo, were revealed to be utterly despicable.⁶ Marzio suddenly became a Pallavicino. A receipt dated 4 December 1562 refers obliquely to Marzio being the son of Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino,⁷ and in Julia's testament of September 1563 she refers to her son as *Martio Mario [Pallavicino] de Vinaija*. Marzio is named on his mother's gravestone as *Marzio Pallavicino*.

6. Cohen 2004

7. SMA tomo 13

In 1566, shortly after Julia's death, Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino wrote his first testament, but did not identify Marzio as his heir. Quite the contrary. Marzio was left nothing. The named heir was his brother, Antonio Pallavicino de Vinaya, who was given the responsibility of acting as Marzio's tutor.¹

1. BARGINUS 1566, f. 454v
2. PAULIS 1563, f. 128v

Marzio died in January 1569, aged 15 years.² A summary of expenditure on his behalf for bespoke clothes and medical expenses during 1567 shows that although his mother had died two years previously, no expense was being spared on his clothes, or education. Only a few days after Marzio's death his father revoked the testament of 1566. In his new testament, dated 1569, he bestowed his wealth on three Roman institutions; the Hospital and orphanage of San Giacomo, the convent of the *Convertite*, and the convent of Santa Caterina dei Funari.³

3. GERARDUS 1569

Intimations of mortality

Julia started using large quantities of oximel and cinnamon in 1562.⁴ Oximel, a mixture of honey and vinegar, was used for masking the taste of some medicines, and also used to dress ulcers. Although only 33 years old she appears to have realized she was suffering from a potentially deadly illness. A year later, in September 1563, the notary Johannes Barginus drafted her testament in her presence and that of Giovanni Francesco.⁵ The executor of the testament, and guardian of Marzio, was named as Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino. She starts by saying that she wanted to be buried in the church of San Rocco, very near her home, together with her late mother, Francesca. The grave was to be before the image of Santa Brigida, and had to be covered with a marble ledger-stone. The saint was, of course, Santa Brigida of Sweden, who settled in Rome in 1349 and dedicated herself to the care of the poor. Julia then made bequests to various Roman institutions, totalling 205 scudi;

4. SMA 152.112r

5. BARGINUS 1563

Chiesa di San Rocco (50 scudi),
Chiesa di San Giuseppe 'prope Marforio' [San Giuseppe dei Falegnami] (50 scudi)
Ospedale di San Rocco (10 scudi)
Ospedale di San Giacomo degli Incurabili (50 scudi)
Monastero della Santissima Trinità dei Monti (10 scudi),
Arciconfraternita del SS. Crocifisso in San Marcello (10 scudi),
Confraternita di Santa Maria del Pianto (10 scudi),
Monastero degli orfani e orfane di Roma, [the Pia casa degli orfani] (10 scudi),
Monastero di Santa Maria Maddalena delle Convertite,
Confraternita del Corpus Christi in San Lorenzo in Lucina (5 scudi)

Julia explains in her testament that these bequests had the aim of absolving her from sin (*in remissione peccati*), thought to be an essential prerequisite for eternal life. There was, however, an exception. This was the bequest to the Monastero delle Convertite. This institution was for the support of repentant prostitutes. The quota was predetermined by law at a fifth of the deceased's estate. It had, apparently, been paid in advance, for there is an entry in the accounts for 1563 recording an *instrumento della liberatione dalle Convertite*.⁶ In Julia's case it would have been about 600 scudi.

6. SMA 26.236r

Julia also requested that there should be a sung mass (*missa cantata*) every year on the anniversary of her death.¹ It was at this time common for testators to request masses to be said for the repose of their souls, but rare that they should ask for them to be sung. Sung masses for the dead, unchanged from those of Julia's day, are still performed in some Roman churches. They are much simpler than the requiems which accompany funerals.

1. BARGINUS 1565,
f. 176v

Julia's substantial bequest to the church of San Giuseppe dei Falegnami, close to the Campidoglio, may indicate that she had some connection with carpentry (*falegnameria*) because in March 1552 she had already spent 10 scudi in the restoration of the chapel of San Giuseppe in that church.² It should be noted that in Julia's day the church of San Giuseppe was often known as San Pietro in Carcere – an ancient church rented by the carpenters guild in 1540, and later rebuilt and renamed.

2. SMA 26.188r

Julia's attachment to her family of origin is shown by several generous bequests. Flaminia, daughter of Julia's sister Giacobba, was left 150 scudi, her niece Francesca Micinelli of Gallese was left 100 scudi, and her nephew, Matteo Tagliacozzo, got 100 scudi.

For inheritance purposes Julia's estate devolved upon her young son Marzio, but in case he were to die without any heirs, as indeed happened, it was to be divided into two equal parts. One part was destined for her nephews and nieces and the other part to the Hospital of San Giacomo degli Incurabili. Consequently, on Marzio's death in 1569, the main house (*casa grande*) passed to Julia's relations, while the two smaller houses adjacent went to the Hospital of San Giacomo. It was because of this bequest to the Hospital that the suburban Roman street *Via Giulia di Gallese* was given its name in 1921.

Julia's debt to Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino

Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino insisted nine months before Julia died that she should admit the financial help he had given her over the years.³ The text of the memorandum is so revealing that it is here given in full, although it is far from clear why he thought it necessary;

3. SMA 152.122r

Io giulia del q. roberto di gallese confesso per la presente esser vera et legitima debitrice del magco Mr giovan francesco palauicino de conto fatto insieme de ogni spesa fatta per me tanto per conto di fabrice dele mie case fatte et spese fatte et salarij et vestire, e calzare per Martio Mio figliuolo tanto a mastro Timoteo quanto a qualsivoglia altra persona e, cosi de ogni altra cosa e denari imprestatomi e cosi quelli lui hauesse hauti da me contanti, si ci riserba come rescossi a mio nome sino a questo di di tutti mi chiamo quieta contenta e sadisfatta e ne li fo ampla quittance e cosi lui a me ogni volta che io li daro scudi settantatre di moneta e baiocchi quarantuno che li resto a dare sino a questo di 20 d'aprile prossimo passato quali prometto pagarneli ad ogni sua requisitione et per cautela dell una e l'altra parte habbiamo sottoscritta la presente di nostra propria mano questo di 20 d'aprile 1564.

I Julia, daughter of the late Roberto of Gallese, declare myself with this note to be the true and legitimate debtor of the magnificent Messer Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino for the money expended on my behalf, both for the restoration of my houses, for the pocket money, clothes and shoes for Marzio my son, for the salary of Master Timoteo, or any other person, and for money which he has lent me, always allowing for the sums which I have paid him, down to today. For all this I declare myself fully satisfied, and so does he [Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino] every time

I pay him 73 scudi and 41 baiocchi which I owe him as of today, 20 April, and I promise to pay them at any further request, and to avoid any misunderstandings we have signed the present memorandum in our own hands this day 20th April 1564.

Master Timoteo was Marzio's tutor.¹ The claim that Giovanni Francesco had paid for the restoration of the dilapidated houses Julia bought overlooks the perpetual mortgage of 270 scudi over her house (*domus magna*) in l'Ortaccio which he obliged her to grant him.² It meant that Julia and her heir, Marzio, had to pay Giovanni Francesco 20 scudi annually. It was not the first mortgage of its kind. Moreover, the very substantial sum of 73 scudi mentioned in the memorandum, which Julia was supposed to pay, appears not to have been either the first or the last. Had she continued to pay it for, say, another five or six years, her debt to Giovanni Francesco would probably have been extinguished.

1. SMA 26.236v

2. VALERIUS 1554

The memorandum above seems to represent an effort by Giovanni Francesco to show that the relationship between him and Julia was not exploitative on his part, or on hers.

The end

The exact date of Julia's death is not recorded, but must have been about 1 February 1565, three days before the burial. The ground-floor bedroom in which she died can be partially reconstructed from the inventory of her possessions compiled on 4 February, a few days after her death (Appendix 1, ff. 180v-182v).

Julia slept in a four-poster bed (*padiglione*) with a bolster, silk covered pillows, sheets, three woollen blankets and a linen bed cover. The bed frame was high enough to keep beneath it a truckle-bed, which could have been pulled out and used by Julia's maid Antonina at night. Antonina would have kept the fire bright (this was the coldest winter of the century) and attended to her mistress's needs. The bedroom had, among other things, a *prie-dieu* with an image of the Madonna in front of it, a walnut writing desk with drawers and two ink pots, a harpsichord, five attractively bound prayer-books, a large mirror (later valued at 4 scudi), a little table 'to eat in front of the fire', three chests of drawers and two silver chandeliers. No books, music scores or carpets are mentioned anywhere in the house, but there were four pictures. Two were in the bedroom, one of Santa Caterina and the other described as being *de fantasia*. Julia also kept her valuables there, including the cash which she entrusted to Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino just before she died. The amount is not recorded, but he told the notary who compiled the inventory that he still had 210 scudi in hand (Appendix 1, f. 183r).

The house Julia died in had also once been used for receiving clients, for one of the windows in the 'downstairs room', next to her bedroom, had a wooden trellis which could have been used by a prostitute, as explained earlier. Few of the beautiful clothes Julia must once have had appear in the inventory. Indeed, in her bedroom there are only petticoats and dressing gowns. The only two dresses she might have worn were in store, giving the impression that she was house-bound. All that remained of the halcyon years were two hats (Appendix 1, f. 179v);

un capello de paglia sottile fodrato di tafetta sottile con suo cordone di seta turchina et d'oro [e]
una berreta di veluto negro con un cordone di velo con una trinetta d'oro a torno

a hat made of fine straw, with a fine silken lining and a hatband of deep blue silk with gold threads [and] a beret of black velvet, the veil trimmed with gold lace

Julia's assets

The inventory compiled a few days after Julia died provides details of her possessions, including loans, mortgages and buildings. The value of the possessions and buildings is, however, not stated. The original cost of the buildings can be roughly estimated, to which has to be added the roughly 1000 scudi she spent in restoring them. From these and other sources a figure for the total value of Julia's assets can be estimated, in scudi, as follows;

Cash and interest-yielding loans.....	800
Houses.....	1800
Furniture and other moveables.....	<u>400</u>
Total.....	3000

It is impossible that Julia could have accumulated 3000 scudi in only 10 years as a courtesan, earning, as she did, no more than 100 scudi a year. She could have saved enough from her earnings to buy dilapidated houses, and perhaps also the furnishings of her houses, but no more. Giovanni Francesco's contribution to the restoration of her houses was substantial, and Julia did not live long enough to repay it.

The Grave of Julia da Gallese

Julia wrote in her testament that she wanted to be buried in the church of San Rocco, very near where she lived. Vincenzo Forcella, who must have seen the stone in 1875, or earlier, records that it was a ledger-stone in front of the third chapel on the right as one enters the church, and remarks that it was adorned by a life-sized engraved figure of a woman in a long dress, alluding to Julia.¹ Neither this gravestone, nor any of the others once set into the floor of the church, survived nineteenth century restorations. The inscription is dated 4 February 1565. This was probably the day Julia was buried, for Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino the day before bought clothes for her funeral. The epitaph below is that recorded by Gaspare Alveri in the seventeenth century, when the stone was still little worn and the inscription legible;²

1. Forcella 1876,
vol. 7, n° 918

2. Alveri 1664, p. 68

JVLIAE ROBERTI FILIAE TAGLIACOSSIAE DOMO
GALLESIO EX SABINIS MATRI OPTIMAE
QVAE VIX. ANNOS XXXV. &

FRANCISCÆ AVIÆ MATERNÆ PIENTISSIMÆ
QVÆ VIX ANN. LX.
MARCIVS PALLAVICINVS POSVIT
IV. NON. FEBRAURII
MDLXV

This stone was placed here by Marzio Pallavicino on 4 February 1565 for Julia Tagliacozzo, daughter of Roberto, native of Gallese in Sabina, his excellent mother; who lived for 35 years, and for Francesca, his most pious grandmother, who lived for 60 years

The stone purports to have been provided by Julia's son Marzio, but he was only 11 years old at the time. It must have been Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino who had arranged it and decided to make public his 'paternity' of Marzio. All that Marzio could have done was to watch his mother being lowered into her grave, and let the tears run down his face.

Reflections

Two questions arise from the forgoing discussion. The first concerns the nature of the relationship between Julia and Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino, while the second is to what extent Julia can be regarded as representative of sixteenth century Roman courtesans.

Julia da Gallese died unremarked by her contemporaries, and never wrote anything that has survived, but was fortunate to have had Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino, a man well versed in finance, as a mentor. To see his influence it is sufficient to compare the loan contract of September 1544, when she started her career aged 15 years, with the memorandum she underwrote in April 1564, only months before she died, which attest to the financial help she had had from Giovanni Francesco. Both documents reveal his firm, not to say iron hand. Without it, Julia could have ended her days in relative poverty, like Tullia d'Aragona, known for her literary output.¹

1. Hairston 2014

Tullia worked near the Piazza di Campo Marzio in 1549 and, like Julia, paid an annual rent of 40 scudi for her premises. But when she died in Trastevere in 1556 the inventory of the personal effects and furniture valued them at 232 scudi, including 43 scudi in cash.² Most of her jewels had been pawned to Antonio Trivulzio, Bishop of Toulon, for 45 scudi. No credits or buildings are listed in the inventory, but nevertheless Tullia hoped that what little she left would suffice to maintain and educate her young son, Celio.

2. ROMAULIS 1556b
f. 81v

Julia's wealth was quite similar to that of her contemporary, the renowned Isabella de Luna. Isabella's assets when she died in 1564 were 1150 scudi in cash and a house valued at 2500 scudi.³ Isabella bequeathed her house to the church of San Salvatore alle Coppelle, leaving her heir Cardinal Farnese almost nothing after paying her debts of 540 scudi and the quota of 600 scudi due to the Monastery of the Convertite, based on the value of the net assets. Isabella, however, had two servants, one an African slave girl called Scilla.⁴ Julia, it will be recalled, had but one servant.

3. SMA tomo 14

4. ZAPPI 1564,
f. 175r

Why Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino should have spent so much time and money serving Julia's interests invites speculation. Alexandra Kolega has claimed that he had been delegated by Cardinal Farnese to act as legal guardian to the courtesans Julia da Gallese and Isabella de Luna.¹ She does not, however, cite any documentary evidence of any such instructions. Giovanni Francesco's link with Isabella de Luna was merely to act as liquidator of her debts, as he was instructed to do by Isabella's heir Cardinal Farnese.²

1. Kolega 2015, pp. 48 & 77

2. SMA tome 14

It has been suggested by Alessandra Camerano that Julia was the concubine of Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino.³ However, it has already been shown that the relationship between them was not parasitic. Furthermore, Giovanni Francesco and Julia did not live together. It is clear from his first testament, written in the sacristy of Sant'Agostino in 1566, that he had his own home nearby, probably in the nearby Palazzo Pallavicino, with several servants.⁴ The fact that Julia had a child called 'Marzio Pallavicino' proves nothing because, as already pointed out, he was not accepted as an heir by his putative father. Marzio was almost certainly the child of a Giustini.

3. Camerano 2022, p. 96

4. BARGINUS 1566

Whereas the amorous affairs of courtesans are well-known to have had a limited duration, Giovanni Francesco stayed by Julia for twenty years, till the moment she died, indicating the existence of an obligation well beyond the sphere of romantic love. Could Julia be the daughter of Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino? This would explain his benevolence towards her, and is not contradicted by the fact that she had the surname Tagliacozzo and several close relations with the same surname. However, if Julia had been the daughter of Giovanni Francesco she would probably have been baptised with his surname, for it was usual in sixteenth century Rome for the illegitimate children of noblemen to be given the surname of their real father. One could cite, for example, Cardinal Alessandro Farnese who had a child called Clelia Farnese, born in 1556 of an unknown mother, only two years after Marzio.

One might also speculate that Giovanni Francesco had an affective link with Francesca Tagliacozzo, rather than her daughter Julia, but there is nothing to prove it. It has to be admitted that there are at present insufficient data to reach a definite conclusion on the relationship between Julia, her mother Francesca and Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino.

The question of whether Julia da Gallese was representative of the courtesans of the city is easier to answer. She was not, if only because she was a house-owner. The 1517 census of Rome shows that only 2% of all the prostitutes were described as such.⁵ Furthermore, an examination of the income and expenditure account for the Monastery of the Convertite for the year 1572 shows that out of a total income of 3592 scudi only 687 scudi came from the levy on 'curiale morte', i.e. deceased prostitutes.⁶ If this year is representative then almost all the levy could have come from one or two particularly successful women, who were house-owners like Isabella de Luna or Julia da Gallese. Particularly successful women are, by definition, not representative.

5. Gnoli 1894

6. SMA tome 14

In summary, Julia made the money she hoped for, had a supportive man at her side, and a child which survived her. Her early death was not unusual for the sixteenth century. The thing she still wished, as her lost volume of memoirs shows, was to be remembered.

Acknowledgements

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References cited

Names of notaries are in capital letters
ASC, Archivio Storico Capitolino
ASR, Archivio di Stato, Roma

- Alveri 1664
Gasparo Alveri. *Della Roma in ogni stato... Parte seconda*. Roma 1664.
- Baglione 1639
Giovanni Baglione. *Le nove chiesa di Roma*. Roma 1639.
- Bandello 1554
Matteo Bandello. *La terza parte de le novelle del Bandello*. Lucca 1554.
- BARGINUS 1563
Johannes Petrus Barginus. [*Testamento di Julia Tagliacozzo de Gallese*]. 9 settembre 1563. ASR, Notai del Tribunale dell'Auditor Camerae, vol. 533, ff. 782r 785r.
- BARGINUS 1565
Johannes Petrus Barginus. *Inventarium bonorum quondam d. Julie Tagliacotii de Galesio.... 4 februari 1565*. ASR, Notai del Tribunale dell'Auditor Camerae, vol. 536, ff. 179r 183r.
- BARGINUS 1566
Johannes Petrus Barginus. [*Testamento di Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino*]. 17 Aprile 1566. ASR, Notai del Tribunale dell'Auditor Camerae, vol. 538, ff. 453r 455r.
- Berra 1932
Luigi Berra. 'Cinque lettere inedite di Lelio Capilupi'. *Archivio della R. Società romana di Storia Patria*, vol. 53 (1932), pp. 357 373.
- Bertolotti 1884
Antonio Bertolotti. *Artisti subalpini in Roma nei secoli 15, 16 e 17: ricerche e studi negli archivi romani*. Mantova 1884.
- Brantôme 1876
Pierre de Bourdeille. *Oeuvres complètes de Pierre de Bourdeille seigneur de Brantôme*. vol. 9, Paris 1876.
- Buccino 2011
Laura Buccino. 'Sculptures displayed and sculptures discovered in Piazza Colonna'. In: Eugenio La Rocca, *La Galleria di piazza Colonna*. Roma 2011, pp. 213 229.
- Calcaterra 2004
Francesco Calcaterra. *Corti e cortigiane nella Roma barocca*. Roma 2004.
- Camerano 2022
Alessandra Camerano. 'La "señora" delle cortigiane romane. Isabella de Luna fra "utilitas, aequitas, honestas"'. In: Marina Formica (ed.) *Presenza femmili a Roma nella lunga Età moderna*. Roma 2022, pp. 89 102.
- Cohen 2004
Thomas V. Cohen. *Love and death in Renaissance Italy*. Chicago 2004.
- Delumeau 1957 1959
Jean Delumeau. *Vie économique et sociale de Rome dans la seconde moitié du XVI^e siècle*. 2 vols., Paris 1957–1959.
- Falda 1676
Giovanni Battista Falda. *Nuova Pianta et Alzata della Città di Roma con tutte le Strade Piazze et Edificii de Tempii*. Roma 1676.
- Forcella 1869 1884
Vincenzo Forcella. *Iscrizioni delle chiesa e d'altri edifici di Roma dal secolo XI fino a ai giorni nostri*. 14 vols., Roma 1869 1884.
- Franco 1580
Veronica Franco. *Lettere familiari a diversi della S. Veronica Franca. All'illustriss. et reverendiss. Monsig. Luigi D'Este Cardinale*. Venezia c.1580.
- GERARDUS 1569
Jacobus Gerardus. [*Testamento di Giovanni Francisco Pallavicino*]. 21 Januarii 1569. ASR, Notai del Tribunale dell'Auditor Camerae, vol. 3557, ff. 135r 138r.

- Gnoli 1894
Domenico Gnoli. 'Descriptio Urbis o Censimento della popolazione di Roma avanti il sacco borbonico'. *Archivio della Società Romana di Storia Patria*, vol. 17 (1894), pp. 375-520.
- Gnoli 1939
Umberto Gnoli. *Topografia e toponomastica di Roma medioevale e moderna*. Roma 1939.
- Hairston 2014
Julia L. Hairston. *The poems and letters of Julia d'Aragona and others*. Toronto 2014.
- Hunter 1996
John Hunter. *Girolamo Siciolante, pittore da Sermoneta (1521–1575)*. Roma 1996.
- Kolega 2015
Alexandra Kolega. *Pia casa degli orfani di Santa Maria in Aquiro e Monastero dei Santi Quattro Coronati Collegio Salviati: archivio storico 1320–1893 inventario*. Roma 2015.
- Lanciani 1903
Rodolfo Lanciani. *Storia degli scavi di Roma e notizie intorno le collezioni romane di antichità*. vol. 2, Roma 1903.
- Lee 1985
Egmont Lee (ed.). *Descriptio Urbis: the Roman census of 1527*. Roma 1985.
- LOTTUS 1564
Quintilius Caesar Lottus. [*Debiti di Giovanni Domenico Surrentino*]. 19 Mai 1564. Notai del Tribunale dell'Auditor Camerae, vol. 3925, ff. 149r 149r.
- Masson 1975
Georgina Masson. *Courtesans of the Italian Renaissance*. London 1975.
- Mendoza 2016
Roberto Mendoza. *Il peccato e il tributo: prostitute e fisco nella Roma del '500*. Canterano 2016.
- Montaigne 1889
Michel de Montaigne. *Journal de voyage de Michel de Montaigne en Italie, par la Suisse et l'Allemagne en 1580 et 1581, Nouvelle édition*. Città di Castello 1889.
- Mutini 1975
Claudio Mutini. 'Lelio Capilupi'. *Dizionario biografica degli italiani*, vol. 18 (1975).
- PAULIS 1563
Hubertus de Paulis. [*Benefattori dell'Ospedale di San Giacomo*] 9 septembris 1563. ASR, Ospedale di San Giacomo, busta 24, benefattore 1515 1700, ff. 128r & 128v.
- Piazza 1698
Carlo Bartolomeo Piazza. *Eusevologio Romano: ovvero delle opere pie di Roma*. Roma 1698.
- Renazzi 1803 1806
Filippo Maria Renazzi. *Storia dell'università degli studi di Roma detta comunemente 'La Sapienza'*. 4 vols., Roma 1803 1806.
- Rodolfo & Volpi 2014
Alessandra Rodolfo, Caterina Volpi (eds.). *Vestire i palazzi. Stoffe, tessuti e parati negli arredi e nell'arte del Barocco*. Città del Vaticano 2014.
- ROMAULIS 1556a
Felix de Romaulis. [*Censo a favore di Julia da Gallese*]. 7 octobris 1556. ASR, Notai del Tribunale dell'Auditor Camerae, vol. 6298, ff. 201r et seq.
- ROMAULIS 1556b
Felix de Romaulis. *Inventarium rerum et bonorum mobilium q. d. Tulie de aragonia curialis*. 23 Aprilis 1556. ASR, Notai del Tribunale dell'Auditor Camerae, vol. 6298, ff. 79r 82v.
- VALERIUS 1554
Pompeus Valerius. *Venditio et impositio census v 20 facta a Julia de Gallesio in favore francisci Pallavicini super Domo in via nuncupata della Croce in Regione Campi Martij*. 11 Septembris 1554. ASR, Ospedale San Giacomo, busta 26, ff. 102r 105v.
- ZAPPI 1564
Johannes Dominicus Zappi. [*Testamento di Isabella de Luna*]. 27 Julii 1564. ASC, Archivio Urbano, sez. 1, vol. 856, ff. 172r 178v.

Appendix 1

Inventory of the effects of Julia Tagliacozzo da Gallese in 1565

Inventarium bonorum quondam d. Julie Tagliacotii de Galesio. 4 februarii 1565.
Archivio di Stato, Roma, Notai del Tribunale dell'Auditore Camerae, vol. 536, ff. 179r-183r.

f. 179r

Inventarium bonorum quondam dominae Julie Tagliacotii de Galesio ad requisitionem et ad instantiam domini Johannis Francisci Pallavicini tutoris et pro tempore curatoris Martii Marii eiusdem dominae Julie filii heredis ac testamenti eiusdem dominae Julie executoris...

Inventory of the effects of the late Madam Julia Tagliacozzi from Gallese, made at the request of Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino, for time being guardian of her son and heir Marzio Mario, and executor of her testament...

Unam domum magnam sitam in regione campi martii iuxta plateam condopulam sive hortacii dictam la casa grande

The main house in Piazza Condopulam [Piazza di Monte d'Oro], ore l'Ortacci, in rione Campo Marzio

Aliam domum contiguam superscritae et ab ea divisam ad effectum illam separatim locandi

Another house next to the above [main house], separated from it to let it

Aliam domum iuxta eandem Plateam prope angulum versus plateam in via dicta ... quam dicta Julia tempore sui obitus inhabitabat

Another house on the corner of the same square [Piazza di Monte d'Oro], in which Madam Julia lived, and died

Inventarium de bonis mobilibus et Pro ex[tent]ibus in quadam **cam[er]a superiore ultimo** dicta domus

Inventory of the contents of **the uppermost room** of the last named house

Doi materassi

Two mattresses

Doi capezali de lana con le coperte de trelicio

Two bolsters stuffed with wool, covered with ticking

Doi cussini ...

Two pillows

lana negra per un altro materasso

Black wool to stuff a mattress

Tralicio per un capezale et un cussinetto separati

Ticking to cover a bolster and a pillow

doi banchetti da letto torniti con cinque tavole da letto

Two sets of steps, of five treads each, to reach a bed

una credenza di legno alta da tenere robbe

A wooden sideboard

doe cinte de spada de veluto una bianca e una rossa

Two velvet sword belts, one white, the other red

un Paro di Pedonelle de Raso bianco da donna

A pair of white satin slippers for a woman

una spadina con doi frodri de veluto uno bianco e l'altro rosso

A sword with two velvet scabbards, one white, the other red

doi ventagli uno de piume e l'altra di paglia

Two fans, one of feathers, the other of straw

un corame de tavola con sei pelle rosse e sei fresi d'oro a torno

A gilded leather table cover, with red pearls and a golden frieze

un paro de Calzini Rossi

A pair of red socks

una cassa de legname vecchia

An old wooden chest

un paro di lenzuoli boni con reticelle bruti

doi forziere vecchio

quattro mazi di lino sconeso

f. 179v

un pezo de tovagliole novi de numero trentaotto

un naspo da conochia lavorato [inlaid] ala damaschina

piatti laccorate depinti con certe tazze e una scudella
coperchate numero in tutto trentacinque

nella medesima camera una campana da stilare

una boticella di rame da mettre in fresco

un vaso di rame da tenere profumo

in un altra camera a paro a l'altra

un padiglione di tela bianca

una lettiera con le sue tavole

tre lenzuoli negri

una scanzia alta di legname

trent otto coppie e mezo di filato de diverse tra stoppa
lino e canape

un naspo col il manicho di ferro

doi gracoili da conciare il lino

nella sala di sopra

un paro di forzieri grandi fod[rato] di tela azura in uno
dei quali si stavano dentro un capello de paglia sottile
fodrato di tafetta sottile con suo cordone di seta
turchina et d'oro

una berreta da veluto negro con un cordone di velo co
una trinetta [merletto] d'oro atorno

doi cussini grandelli di raso rosso con trine d'oro a
torno

un cussinetto picole di rarmesino rosso da rose

una vesta con le sue maniche di reverso rosso nova

un altro paro di maniche de perpagnano

un tornaletto di raso incarnatio recamato di veluto giallo

un paro di banchetti da letto tornati

doi telari de impan[n]ate

Two good bed sheets with worn out lace edging

Two old strong boxes

Four hanks of linen

Thirty-eight new napkins

A [ceramic] spindle decorated *alla damaschina*

A set of 38 lacquered plates, including cups and a
serving bowl with its lid

A still, in the same room

A copper container for chilling [a liquid]

A copper vase for perfume

Another room at the same level as that above

White plain weave material for a four-poster bed

A complete bed

Three black sheets

A high wooden bookshelf

Thirty-eight and a half hanks of raw cotton, linen and
hemp thread

A spindle with its iron handle

Two racks for dressing linen

in the upper room

Two large strong boxes covered with blue cloth. In one
was a hat of fine straw lined with soft taffeta and with a
hat-band of dark blue silk and gold thread

A black velvet beret, the veil trimmed with gold lace

Two large cushions covered with red satin trimmed with
gold lace

Two small cushions covered with fine rose-coloured silk

A new red dress with [detachable] red-lined sleeves

Another pair of sleeves of Perpignan muslin

A bed surround of red satin embroidered with yellow
velvet

Two sets of steps to reach a bed

Two wooden window frames

una galosi [gelosia] anda fuocho

un tavolino col sue telaro vecchio

una matera di legno con sale e finocchio dentro

un altro forziere vecchio voto

un telaro di un quadro

f. 180r

nella sala di basso

una tavola longhetta con le suoi trispedi con un corame vecchio di sopra con dodeci pelle intera quattro dimezati con suoi fresi d'oro a torno

una credenza di legno con un corame rosso con fresi d'oro a torno sopra detta credenza

doi sedie di corame vecchie

un altra simile da donna

quattro sediole de paglia basse

un banquetto de legno

doi quadri di legno con fresi d'oro a torno depinti con una venere cioe uno e laltro una cleopatra

un altro quadro grande di tela quale dicano esser della sig^{ra} Julia neap^{na} con una cornice a torno di noce

un paro de capifoghli bassa d'ottone gli ferri da focho

una impanata fatta a gialosia e l'altra impanata

una gialosia di legno su le fenestre de detta sala

un scalda letto

emqr candarieri d'ottone

una cassetina di legno da camera

una lucerna d'ottone dal oleo

nel cucina da basso

una credenza di legno vecchia

un paro de capifuochi

una gratacasa

doi padelle di rame

un treletto di rame

una graticola di ferro

una schiumatora di rame

A fire screen

A small table

A wooden vase containing salt and fennel [seeds]

Another old strong box, with nothing in it

A picture frame

in the downstairs room

A long table supported on trestles covered with old gilded leather ornamented by 12 whole pearls and four half pearls, and a golden frieze

A wooden side board covered by red gilded leather with a golden frieze

Two chairs covered with old gilded leather

Another similar chair for a woman

Four low chairs with straw seats

A wooden dining table

Two painted panels, each with a golden frieze, one depicting a Venus and the other a Cleopatra

A large picture on canvas, said to belong to Signora Julia, Napolitano, with a walnut frame

A pair of brass fire dogs, and iron fire tools

Two window frames, one with a wooden shutter

A trellised wooden screen in the windows of this room

A bedwarmer

Brass candle-sticks

A small wooden box

A brass oil lamp

in the downstairs kitchen

An old wooden sideboard

A pair of fire dogs

A grater

Two copper frying pans

A copper trellis

A iron sieve

A copper skimmer

un trisprede picolino	A small tripod
<i>f. 180v</i>	
doi spiedi uno piccolo e una grande	Two spits, one small, the other large
doe conche d rame	Two copper basins
un soletto di rame	A copper baking tray
una caldarella di rame da lavare le mane	A large copper basin to wash one's hands
un cucumetto di rame	A copper coffee pot
doi trespiede grandi di ferro	A large iron tripod
un mortaro di marmoro meschio	A marble mortar
doi altri mortari di pietra	Another two mortars made of stone
un schumerello [<i>schiumaiola</i>] e un altra schiumalora di ferro	Two skimmers, one made of iron
un schomerello grande de rame da versare la bugata	A large copper strainer for draining the washing
doi secchii con le cathene da pozzo	Two buckets with chains [to lower them down a well]
una girella da bronzo	A bronze pulley wheel
cocome una da fare la bugata e una ... per terra	A basin to wash clothes, and another
un cucumetto di rame vecchio	A small copper basin, rather old
la tavola della cucina	The kitchen table
certi piatti e pignatte e tegame e bichieri	A number of plates, pots and glasses
una caldara grande senza manicho di tenuta di some quattro in circa	A large container without handles containing <i>c.</i> 460 litres [for wine]
un altra caldara un poco piu bassa	Another, smaller container
un caldarello di rame col il suo manicho	A copper container with handles
doi carratelli [<i>caratelli</i>] vecchi	Two small barrels, rather old
doi tinoze una grande e una piccola	Two tubs, one big, the other small
doi para de trespidi di legno da fare la bugata	Two pairs of wooden dollies for washing clothes
una vettina grande da acqua	A large container for water
doe vettine da olio piccole vote	Two small empty containers for olive oil
un imbutatore	A funnel
nella camera piana nella prima sala	in the room next to the first [downstairs]
in una cassa di noce lavorata sei linzuoli tutti bianchi schietti	A walnut chest containing six perfectly white sheets
un altro paro di linzuoli con doe fettucie di seta cremasina	A pair of sheets with two bright red ribbons
doe tovaglie nove	Two new tablecloths

f. 181r

altre doe tovaglie de una canna l'una in pezza
tredici tovaglie in pezzo
due altre tovaglie usate
tovaglioli sei di lenzo rigate
un paro di linzuoli piccoli con reticelle bianche
tre succatori [*asciugatoi*] in pezza ala turchese novi
una a[r]matura di curtina da donna biancha
tre guarnelli bianchi alla turchesca
dodeci camise da donne usate
un paro di guanti perfumati novi
un paro da fodrette con fettucce di seta cremisina
tela di lino arotolata in pezze di peso libre vinti
doe fodrette de capezzali lunghi quattro con fettucce di seta
un paro di fazoletti lavorati di seta cremesina e d'argento
un altro fazoletto lavorato in seta schietta di colore
una scufia lavorata a seta rossa e altri colori e filo d'oro
una vesta di rascia negra quasi nova
cinque scufie de piu sorte usate
cenali [*zinali*] vecchi quattro
veli de spala sei
un paro di fodrette bianche nove
cinque tovaglie usate cioe doi de lenza e tre di R'ama

f. 181v

doi tele di linzuola di cortina usate
fodrette tre usate con fettucce bianche e una rossa
doi altri fodrette usate con fettucce d'oro vecchie
doi para di calcette fatte a guccia [*guscia*]
tre para di maniche de guanciaie bianche
filato in doe foderette inglomerato e d'orinale in tutto libre sette
tre sucatori [*asciugatoi*] d'orinale bianche

Another two tablecloths, each 3 metres long
Thirteen tablecloths
Two more tablecloths, used
Six tablecloths of ridged linen
A pair of small patterned sheets
Three new, turquoise-coloured towels
The frame for a white fabric screen, for a woman
Three white undervests of Turkish design
Twelve shirts for a woman, all used
A new pair of perfumed gloves
A pair of pillow cases with bright red silk ribbons
Linen fabric in rolls weighing c. 10 kg
Two bolster covers with red silk ribbons
A pair of bright red silk handkerchiefs embroidered with silver
Another handkerchief of white silk
A bonnet of red silk and other colours and gold thread
A dress of black, thick wool, almost new
Five bonnets of various kinds, used
Four old aprons
Six veils covering head and shoulders
A pair of new, white pillow cases
Five tablecloths, two of linen and three of damask, all used

Two curtains, used
Three pillow-cases, two with white ribbons and one with a red ribbon, all used
Two more pillowcases with ribbons of gold, used
Two pairs of dancing shoes of finest leather
Three pairs of sleeves made of white cotton
Two bags of ravelled yarn weighing together c.2.5 kg, for use with the chamber pot
Three white towels for use with the chamber pot

un altro sucatore lavorato con fettucia di seta rossa	A towel embroidered with red silk ribbons
un tornaletto di tela bianca romanesca con reticelle e una frangetta bianca a Pieve	A bed surround of white canvas, roman style, with nets and a white fringe from Pieve
tre altri tovaglioli di lenza rigati	Three tablecloths of patterned linen
tre altri dozenali usati	Three cheap tablecloths
un braccio di tela nova grossa	A piece of coarse new cotton cloth 0,67 metres long
una coperta di raso rosso racamata di veluto giallo	A red satin counterpane embroidered with yellow velvet
un Padiglione usato di filo indente [<i>filondente</i>] con fettucce di seta nera col suo tornaletto usato	A canopy, or tester, of coarse cotton fabric decorated with black silk ribbons, together with the bed surround
quattro tapeti piccoli da forzieri	Four small carpets to put under strong boxes
doi altri fodrette usate	Two pillow-cases, used
doi candalieri d'argento novi alla napolitana	Two new chandeliers in the Napolitan style
un capello de armesino negro con un cordone e un fioccho	A hat of black, fine silk with a hat-band and bow
una scatola	A box
una corona de corali con bottoncini e rosette tramesate con segnacoli d'oro smaltati	A coral crown decorated with glazed gold rosettes
un vezzo di perle	A string of pearls
un altra corona de hebbano con signacoli d'argento e bottoncini	An ebony crown with silver decorations
un centurino di perle picoline concio in recame	A lace belt decorated with little pearls
una conciatura di testa con certe perlette	A veil with little pearls
doi officioi uno coperto di veluto e ermosino e l'altra con certi rechami d'oro con certe fibie d'argento pur' de veluto ermes...	Two prayer books, one bound in velvet and silk, the other bound in velvet and silk decorated with gold, and with a silver clasp
un cassetino di ferro piccolo	A small iron box
una lumaca di madre di perle	A Nautilus of mother of pearl
bottoni d'argento venti tre con certi Patre Nostri di diaspri sfilati	Twenty-three silver beads together with some beads of coral and diaspre signifying Our Father, unthreaded
una medaglia con un camelo	A medal with a cameo
un paro di maniglie d'oro	A pair of gold bracelets
<i>f. 182r</i>	
un diacinto [<i>giacinto</i>] e una turchina ligati in oro e una fede pur d'oro	A brooch with a zircon and a turquoise set in gold, and a wedding ring also of gold
un busolottino d'argento con una corgniola [<i>chalcedony</i>] e un diaspro da stagnare sangue legati in oro	Jewels of chalcedony and diaspre, together with a silver coin, set in gold and supposed to staunch blood
una medaglietta d'oro cioe una faustina	A brooch made from a Roman coin called a <i>Faustina</i>
tredecim scudi d'oro in oro e cinque ducati de camera	Thirteen gold <i>scudi</i> and five ducats

un'altra scudo d'oro in oro	Another gold <i>scudo</i>
vinticinque scudi d'oro in tanti Pauli e doi Giulii	Thirty-five gold <i>scudi</i> in <i>Paoli</i> , and two <i>Giulii</i>
una medaglia del duca ottavio d'argento con tre moneted'argento	Silver commemorative medal showing Duke Ottavio [Farnese], together with three silver coins
una coperta di tela bianca imbottita a mandolette	A white cotton quilt sewn with an almond pattern
una ciamarra [zimara] di raffia negra	A dressing gown of black raffia
una sottana [petticoat] di Perpegnano	A petticoat of Perpignan muslin
un'altra sottana di reverso rosso	Another petticoat, red inside
una ciamarra [zimara], di careassona bisa	A dressing gown of Carcassonne silk
una coperta de dobletto bianca	A counterpane of white linen and cotton
un altro lenzuoli bruti usati	An old sheet
doe cussinetti con due fodrette di seta eremesina	Two little pillows with fine silk covers
doi caperzzali di tela longhi usati	Two long bolsters covered with ticking, used
un paro di banquetti torniti con le sue tavole	Two sets of [wooden] steps
doe scuffie di seta rossa	Two red silk bonnets
un saccone di pagliacio da letto	A straw mattress for a bed
un quadro de santa Catherina	A picture of Saint Catherine
un altro quadro de fantasia	Another picture <i>de fantasia</i>
doi calamari ala napolitano una intarsiato e l'altro lisso	Two Neapolitan style ink pots, one inlaid, the other not
un gravicembolo	A harpsichord
un specchio di cristallo	A glass mirror
un studiolo ala napolitana da noce	A walnut Neapolitan style writing desk
tre saponiitti	Three bars of soap
una panno de spala	A shoulder cloth
un materasso con un tornaletto	A mattress together with a bed surround
un bacile e una brachetta [brocchetta] alla faentina	A basin and water jug of Faenza porcelain
un torchio da panno listato	An ironing press
una banchetta piccola da mangear a presso il fuocho	A little table to eat in front of the fire
una tavoletta con la cassetina sotto	A small table with a drawer
una cassetina alla napolitana intarsiata	A little box inlaid in the Neapolitan style
un paro di tripiedi da tenere il gravicimbolo	Two tripods to support the harpsichord
in un altro cassetino giulii otto	A little box containing 8 <i>Giulii</i>
un frascho racamato	
tre officioli della madonna con la coperta lavorata d'azuro	Three books of hours, the covers decorated in blue

f. 182^v

un altarucio, e un quadro d'una madonna con un da scabello [sgabello] da ingenuochiarsi

un stucio [astuccio] voto

doi materasi grandi e doi piccoli da carriola

una carriola col suo paglaricio

un capezzale piccolo

tre coperte di lana bianca vecchie

le impanate dele fenestre de detta camera e del studiolo

un crucifisso

un censo annuo de scudi quindeci d'oro in oro imposto per Ms Pompeo Justino da Castello sopra una sua casa posta in parione dove lui abita da pagarsi di sei in sei mesi anticipatamente et a detta m^a Giulia venduto per 7 cento cinquanta simili, con securita dem pietro paulo Justino et ms Alexandro cinquino...Felice de Romaulis not. del A. C. 7 ottobre 1556

un credito di scudi novanta Ms Giulio albero di veletri con securita de Justino de Rossi scrittore apostolico ... medesimo notaio 4 agosto 1557...gia stato pagato una parte e restar scudi trenta in cerca

un altro credito de scudi cento d'oro devuti per ms paulo goro... per gli atti di ms felice de Romaulis not[ar]o sotto di 15 d'augosto 1557 quale credo non esser exigibil per esser detto Ms Paulo falitto

f. 183^r

un altro credito de scudi ducento di moneta de ms Cosmo Justino cavalier del S. pietro in compagnia sopra detto officio con securita de ms Pompeo de Justino e Ms francesco Belhomo...sopradetto felice [de Romaulis] notaro, 15 de genaro 1558

un altro credito de scudi ducento di moneta in compagnia a Ms Thomaso armentiero Cavalier de S. Paulo sopra detto ufficio con securita de ms Gentile petromathei de albertoni et vincenzo perna da frascati... per li atti del sopradetto notaio [Felice de Romaulis] sotto di ultimo de marzo 1559

un altro credito de scudi novanta di moneta con moyse rubin et Rubin suo figliolo hebrei ...d'augosto 1564 da pagarsi fra dieci mesi...Alessandro de Romaulis, notaio,

e piu [Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino] dechiara haver^o in mano scudi ducento et dieci di moneta e baiocchi cinquanta e nove per tanti che detta M^a giulia gli dette de contanti in serbo prima che morisse.

A prie-dieu, i.e. an altar, a picture of the Madonna and a kneeling stool

An empty purse

Two large mattresses, and two small, for truckle beds

A truckle bed with its straw mattress

A small bolster

Three old, white woollen blankets

The windows of this room and the study

A crucifix

A mortgage over a house in rione Parione belonging to Mr Pompeo Giustini of Castello, in which he lives, giving an annual interest of 15 *scudi* to be paid every six months in advance, and sold to Madam Julia for 150 *scudi*, guaranteed by Pietro Paolo Justino and Alexandro Cinquino...notary, Felix de Romaulis 7 October 1556

A credit of 90 scudi in the name of Mr Giulio Albero di Velletri...drafted by the same notary [Felice de Romaulis], 4 August 1557...a part has already been repaid, 30 scudi is outstanding

Another credit of 100 scudi, in the name of Paolo Goro...notary, Felix de Romaulis, 15 August 1557, not recoverable due to the bankruptcy of Mr Paulo

Another credit of 200 scudi in the name of Cosimo Justino, knight of San Pietro, guaranteed by Pompeo de Justino and Francesco Belhomo...notary, Felice [de Romaulis], 15 January 1558

Another credit of 200 *scudi* in the name of Thomaso Armentiero, knight of San Paulo, with security of Gentile Pietromathei de Albertoni and Vincenzo Perna from Frascati...notary, Felice de Romaulis, 31 March 1559

Another credit of 90 scudi in the name of Moyse Rubin and his son, Jews...notary, Alessandro de Romaulis, 31 August 1564

Finally, Giovanni Paolo Pallavicino declares that he has in hand 210 *scudi* and 59 *baiocchi* of the money Madam Julia entrusted to him just before she died.